

SOCIO-PSYCHOLOGICAL COMPETENCE AND EFFECTIVENESS OF INTERNAL AFFAIRS IN THE ACTIVITIES OF PSYCHOLOGISTS

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Annotation: the article examines the socio-psychological competence of leaders necessary for the implementation of effective management activities. Some individual qualities of the personality of managers are studied, which are characterized by a high level of development of management and socio-psychological competence, as well as possible methods and forms of measurement, analysis and assessment of professionally important qualities of an individual. This means that the study of the personality of the leader and aspects of managerial activity should be carried out on the basis of an integrated approach to the effective professional development of the personality of the leader and the formation of a worthy attitude towards his professional activity. At the same time, complex assessment includes an assessment of the activity as a whole, the entire volume of its functions and the personality of the leader. The purpose of the article is to determine the degree of importance of the professional and psychological training of leaders for their socio-psychological competence and effectiveness in management activities, as well as for the correct Organization of training of the executive personnel Reserve.

Keywords: professional-psychological training, socio-psychological competence, executive personnel reserve, management psychology, leadership psychology, leader psychology, leader

The goal: An important role in ensuring the professional work of employees of internal affairs bodies is played by the control and use of the socio-psychological potential of communities. This should be taken into account in the filling of units, in individual educational work and professional training of employees, as well as in the selection of optimal styles and methods of leadership, depending on the level of development of the team, the adaptation of all its members to the requirements of the profession and the characteristics of interpersonal relationships.

In order to achieve a high level of efficiency in the official activities of employees of internal affairs bodies, socio-psychological competence and efficiency in the management activities of managers of all levels, as well as the ability of managers to take into account conditions and factors in a holistic relationship, the ability to identify priority areas of management activity and effectively implement their socio-psychological. Therefore, the leader is the choice of Personnel, their training, retraining and subsequent control over their development sometimes have a decisive influence on all processes of managing the communities of internal affairs bodies.

Main part: From the point of view of the issue of conditions of competence of the leader, it is often possible to distinguish such an important category as "general management ability", which can be understood as the ability to combine the whole set of unique qualities (abilities) of a person. We are talking about professional management (psychological) abilities, knowledge, skills and abilities, i.e. about knowledge transformed into certain management procedures that ensure the effectiveness of management activities and are embodied in solving specific management problems [6]. At the same time, management authority is manifested as a system of the leader's internal resources necessary to organize effective leadership for subordinates. However, it should

be remembered that there is no single way to perform any activity, especially management. Considering the factors that describe the essence of successful management activity, it should be noted that this success can be achieved psychologically in different ways. These ways and methods are as diverse as the abilities of a person in general. At the same time, the leader's methods of achieving the goal are individual. Therefore, with all the alternatives of the management process and the diversity of its implementation methods, solving this problem is related to the study of personal aspects of management and, as a result, the choice of individual professional and psychological approaches to the training of individual leaders. It should also be remembered that in the process of increasing the level of management (leadership level), the forming factors and conditions of the activity of management personnel change, the requirements for systematic and analytical-predictive aspects of management increase, and this has a significant impact on the psychological profile of the decisions made. shows and requires leaders to update certain professional and psychological skills and personal characteristics.

The content and purpose of our article is to study the influence and importance of the leader's professional and psychological training, individual qualities of his personality on his further socio-psychological competence. The core of the individual qualities of the person and the social-psychological competence of the leader is, first of all, the social-psychological and management component of the competence of the leader. The management component includes meaningful, resource-temporary and socio-psychological components of the leader's activity [5]. At the same time, management competence is a system of internal resources of the leader necessary to organize effective leadership for subordinates, as well as his work, the nature of the work performed, complex relationships, events and processes, possible methods and means of achieving goals. is presented as a thorough knowledge of.

Since the professional and psychological competence of a leader is a systematic education that reflects the activity of managing people, it is almost impossible to get a holistic picture by evaluating any of its individual aspects, because any system cannot be reduced to the sum of its components, and many things depending on how individual elements are organized (in particular, individual qualities of individuals) in the overall structure. On the other hand, the same psychological characteristics of individuals of different orientations and development levels reveal different effectiveness in team management. The essence of the leader's socio-psychological competence is the leader's willingness to consciously, timely and creatively solve various management problems, as well as the ability to adequately perceive interpersonal perception and interaction, an optimal combination of different management styles. This personal state represents the unity of motivational-value, emotional-voluntary and meaningful-operational components and describes the level of professional development of a person [6; 7]. The main feature of the leader's socio-psychological competence is the individual leadership style. One or another leadership style is chosen not only because it is successful, but also because it allows to achieve as much as possible the goals that are relevant within the scope of the activity and correspond to the system of motivational relations that are more important for the individual.

The leader's success in performing complex functional tasks depends on his professional and psychological preparation for management activities, as well as the level of his socio-psychological competence. According to a number of authors, a leader with a high level of development of management and social-psychological competence is distinguished by the following qualities:

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- ✚ striving for professional and personal growth;
- ✚ objectivity and self-criticism of assessing the level of individual development;
- ✚ breadth of professional, general, management and socio-psychological knowledge;
- ✚ the direction of stable management, which is manifested in understanding the importance of psychological knowledge, skills and abilities for professional activity, believing in the necessity of their formation;
- ✚ high level of personal development;
- ✚ the ability to quickly manage the situation, to respond flexibly to its changes, to solve management problems in accordance with the current situation;
- ✚ the ability to choose the right priority goals;
- ✚ perseverance, determination, energy in achieving team management goals;
- ✚ the ability to create a favorable socio-psychological climate in the team, to avoid conflicts and to resolve them psychologically correctly if they arise;
- ✚ the ability to be responsible for the management decision;
- ✚ the ability to optimally distribute service tasks among subordinates to achieve an effective result;
- ✚ benevolence in communication with subordinates;
- ✚ the ability to influence people without using power;
- ✚ the ability to accurately assign tasks to subordinates based on a good knowledge of their individual psychological characteristics, skillful selection of performers, successful promotion and encouragement of their activities;
- ✚ the ability to organize effective control over the activities of subordinates, make corrections in the process of implementing management decisions. The leader's ability to act within the goals assigned to him, as well as independently establish new ones, indicates a high level of his professional and psychological training and development. At this level of professional and psychological preparation, the manager is able to analyze the trends and prospects of his activity, to consider it in a broad social context, to abandon professional stereotypes that did not justify themselves at the time.

One of the areas of professional and psychological training of candidates for leadership positions is the creation of personnel reserves. "Personnel reserve" means a group of prospective employees organized in the prescribed manner for the purposeful training of leaders of various levels and subsequent appointment in the institution of the body, department, internal affairs bodies. The goal of personnel training for each specific field of leadership is to increase the socio-psychological competence of candidates and their effectiveness in managing teams. The creation of this reserve, among other things, is related to the implementation of the principle of continuity of employees in the internal affairs bodies, which requires the consistent renewal of the heads of the internal affairs bodies, departments, institutions, who show creative initiative, have organizational qualities, and team relations. includes the training and demonstration of young employees who know how to properly organize, have high moral and legal qualities [6].

The main goal of training reserve employees for appointment to the leadership structure of internal affairs bodies is to develop their potential sufficiently to occupy the planned high position. For this, employees should acquire the necessary theoretical knowledge, acquire and improve the skills of organizing the activities of relevant services and departments based on mastering the working methods of the heads of these services, and make reasonable management decisions in

the relevant directions of the activities of internal affairs bodies. they need to develop their skills. The selection of candidates for admission to the personnel reserve is carried out on the basis of the study and assessment of the results of personal and business qualities, as well as organizational abilities. Mandatory conditions for candidates for leadership positions: high level of professional training and service results; have scientific work methods and advanced experience; knowledge of normative legal documents; the ability to actively influence public opinion, create a comfortable environment in the service team. The most important task in the formation of the reserve for the appointment of the management structure is to ensure the identification of the most promising candidates who have the qualities most necessary for professional leadership. To successfully solve this problem, it is necessary to use scientifically based and practical criteria and methods of employee evaluation. The formation of the reserve ensures reliable continuity in filling the leadership positions of internal affairs bodies and minimizes the risk of appointing a leader who does not meet the requirements for it. Thus, the activity of the head of the internal affairs body is multifaceted and is carried out under the influence of various external and internal factors in conditions of certain uncertainty, which requires him to have higher management powers and psychological support for the head. determines the need.

The assessment of the psychological potential of the personnel reserve for candidates allows for targeted implementation of work with the personnel of internal affairs bodies, psychological training, timely prevention of deviant behavior and professional deformation. Assessment of management competence allows to study the personality of managers and employees in the personnel reserve, their ability and readiness to perform management powers and functions. includes the content, criteria, methods and forms of measuring, analyzing and evaluating the process and methods of action. In other words, the psychological study of the personality of the manager and employee who is a candidate for a higher position or included in the personnel reserve for candidacy should be carried out on the basis of a comprehensive approach. At the same time, we mean a comprehensive assessment of the entire activity, its functions and personality, that is, the business, social and individual psychological characteristics of a leader. Currently, there are very wide methodological tools for studying the personality of a leader or employee appointed to a high position. is being used. The main methods of studying the personal and business characteristics of the leading employees of internal affairs bodies, as well as the individual style of managing service groups: psychological test; experience; observation; logical, historical and functional-structural comparison; structural analysis of documents; expert assessment. The diagnostic system of management competence includes the subject, place, psychotechnology, procedure for using diagnostic results, data collection, analysis and interpretation [6].

Materials and methods. In turn, management activities are multifaceted and carried out in many areas. People (by their will and intelligence), knowledge, information and technical means are involved here. All this together forms a complex socio-psychological phenomenon. You can get a lot of information and at the same time not process it (due to a lack of knowledge, skills and qualifications). A balanced, balanced introduction of all elements of managerial activity can give it rationality and efficiency. Thus, the complexity of socio-psychological competence can and should be considered the most important general feature of managerial activity. Attention to the psychological aspects of management activities makes it possible to understand management as a complex mechanism of psychological interaction between people.

Conclusion. In this article, we tried to consider the theoretical aspects of socio-psychological competence of the heads of internal affairs bodies, to reveal the importance of socio-psychological competence in the management activities of the leader, its content, functions and level of development. We tried to draw attention to the socio-psychological characteristics of the competence of the leader and the importance of training the personnel Reserve in the formation of the management structure of internal affairs bodies of all levels. Since the optimal placement of employees is one of the most important factors in the effective functioning of the internal affairs bodies as a whole in the Civil Service and as an integral part of it, our research work is aimed at studying the importance of professional and psychological training of managers in the future for their socio-psychological competence and effectiveness in.

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